

PRINCIPALS' TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES AS CORRELATE OF TEACHERS' JOB EFFECTIVENESS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN OTUOCHA EDUCATION ZONE

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Abstract: The study investigated the relationship between principals' transformational leadership practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 686 teachers in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone. The sample of the study comprised 137 public secondary school teachers in the Zone. Using simple random sampling, the researcher sampled 20 percent of teachers in the zone. Two structured questionnaires were used to collect data for the study. The face validation of the instruments was conducted by three experts in the Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus. The instruments reliability was ascertained through a trial test conducted on 20 teachers of public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone. The data collected was tested for internal consistency using Cronbach Alpha. This yielded reliability coefficients of 0.87 and 0.91 for clusters 1 and 2 respectively with a general reliability coefficient of 0.89 for PTLQ and 0.88 for TJEQ. Out of 137 copies of questionnaires administered, 128 copies were returned in good condition. Pearson product moment correlation was used to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses for the study. Findings revealed that principals' intellectual stimulation practices and individualized consideration practices have a high positive relationship with teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone. Furthermore, findings revealed that principals' intellectual stimulation practices and individualized consideration practices have a significant positive relationship with teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone. The study recommended that the Ministry of Education and Post Primary Schools Services Commission (PPSSC) should organize regular training workshops and seminars to equip principals with skills in transformational leadership, especially in areas of intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration.

Keywords: Principals, Intellectual Stimulation, Individualized Consideration, Teachers Job Effectiveness, Transformational Leadership practices.

Introduction

Education serves as a fundamental pillar for national and economic advancement and is vital for achieving sustainable development. This standpoint is articulated in the National Policy on Education. As noted by the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013), education in the country is premised on the belief that it is a crucial instrument for national development and societal transformation. The Nigerian educational structure comprises

four tiers: pre-primary, primary, secondary, and post-secondary levels (FRN, 2013). This study centres on secondary education. Secondary education refers to the stage that comes after primary education and precedes higher education. It is pivotal as it acts as a bridge between basic and tertiary education and plays a key role in equipping individuals for productive lives within society. According to the FRN (2013), secondary education is delivered following the completion of nine years of basic education. Its general objectives include preparing individuals for meaningful societal participation and further educational pursuits. Teachers are central to the actualisation of these objectives, as they are responsible for carrying out academic tasks.

Teachers are instrumental in enhancing students' learning, educational attainment, and professional development. According to Paschal and Mkulu (2020), teachers influence both individual and institutional success by modelling appropriate behaviour both within and outside the classroom. Their capacity to manage themselves and the school timetable is vital to the overall achievement of school goals. A teacher is essentially one who facilitates the acquisition of knowledge, skills, or values. Rajagopalan (2019) defined a teacher as someone dedicated to the systematic and formal engagement in instructional processes. Similarly, Watti (2018) described a teacher as a professional educator whose duties include instructing, guiding, mentoring, assessing, and evaluating learners. Arop et al. (2020) further emphasised that at the secondary school level, the realisation of educational goals largely depends on the teacher's expertise in lesson planning, classroom management, and student assessment. Consequently, FRN (2013) asserted that the quality and effectiveness of teachers are integral to the success of the education system.

Teachers' job effectiveness refers to how well educators perform their core instructional responsibilities and their overall disposition towards the profession (Arop et al., 2020). In this context, job effectiveness encompasses the ability of teachers to professionally organise their tasks to achieve optimal outcomes in classroom instruction, discipline maintenance, and academic supervision (Onyekwelu, 2024). However, poor performance among secondary school teachers has emerged as a significant obstacle to attaining the objectives of secondary education in the Onitsha Education Zone. This concern is corroborated by findings from Obiekwe and Mbanefo (2019), and further attributed by David-West and Kaegon (2017) to the leadership styles adopted by school principals.

The principal serves as the administrative head and chief executive officer of a secondary school. In the Onitsha Education Zone, the principal is tasked with guiding and overseeing school operations to fulfil educational objectives (Onuorah et al., 2023). As a professional educator, the principal is also involved in curriculum development and mobilising resources to support teaching staff. To fulfil these duties effectively, high interpersonal skills are essential (Obiekwe & Mbanefo, 2019). The current study focuses on the principal as a leader whose role involves facilitating the effective management of educational resources to enhance teaching and learning outcomes.

Leadership entails guiding a team towards the attainment of shared goals. It involves motivating, inspiring, and supporting subordinates in the execution of their responsibilities (Okeke et al., 2023). According to Jidefor (2022), leadership is the capacity to influence a group to achieve set goals, highlighting the importance of shaping behaviours and group dynamics toward common objectives. Leadership can be exercised through various behaviours and approaches, commonly referred to as leadership styles.

Leadership styles represent the methods, behaviours, and attitudes employed by leaders to influence the performance of others. Okumbe (2015) defined leadership style as the specific behaviour adopted by a leader to inspire subordinates to accomplish organisational goals. Achimugu and Obaka (2019) described principals' leadership styles as the approaches principals adopt in managing school affairs. For the purposes of this study, principals' leadership styles refer to the various strategies employed by school heads to influence their staff and foster a conducive learning environment. Asiegbu and Ikwu (2020) identified transformational leadership as a particularly effective style in enhancing teachers' job effectiveness.

Transformational leadership is a modern leadership approach introduced by James MacGregor Burns in 1978. This model views the relationship between leaders and followers as one of mutual elevation (Uzoechina & Oguegbu, 2015). According to Asiegbu and Ikwu (2020), transformational leadership as applied by principals entails motivating teachers to realise institutional objectives by effectively planning, organising, directing, and aligning school expectations with teachers' needs in a way that is both productive and individually motivating. To achieve this, principals are expected to possess traits such as teamwork orientation, effective communication, problem-solving capabilities, adaptability to change, and overall transformational leadership competence. In essence, transformational leadership encompasses shared vision, insight, inspiration, and charisma that result in significant changes in attitudes, beliefs, productivity, and direction within both the organisation and its personnel. Balyer, as cited in Asiegbu and Ikwu (2020), identified four key components of transformational leadership in school settings: inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, individualised consideration, and idealised influence. However, for the purposes of this study, emphasis is placed on intellectual stimulation and individualised consideration.

Intellectual stimulation, on the other hand, is the principal's commitment to fostering innovation and creativity among staff. This is achieved by encouraging teachers to challenge assumptions, reframe issues, and explore new strategies for problem-solving. Igwenwanne and Obasi (2024) described intellectual stimulation as the leadership trait that cultivates creative thinking among subordinates, enabling them to become more effective decision-makers. It involves providing a sound rationale for school decisions while promoting innovative contributions from the teaching staff.

Individualised consideration entails recognising and addressing the unique needs and abilities of individual teachers. It reflects the principal's capacity to act as both a mentor and advisor, offering personalised support and guidance (Efendi, 2015). Principals demonstrating this trait are sensitive to the differences among staff members and create opportunities for professional growth and personal recognition. According to Igwenwanne and Obasi (2024), individualised consideration is exhibited when school leaders provide consistent encouragement, support, and developmental opportunities tailored to individual teachers, while also acknowledging their achievements and contributions. Igwenwanne and Obasi (2024) asserted that the transformational leadership dimensions of inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualised consideration have the potential to significantly enhance teachers' job effectiveness. In a study conducted in Bayelsa State, Mba and Okoko (2024) discovered a high positive correlation between principals' intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration with teachers' productivity. Their research, involving both principals and teachers across various schools, highlighted the critical role of these leadership dimensions in enhancing teacher performance. Similarly,

Akinnubi and Adeoye (2024), working in Oyo State, found that when principals demonstrated intellectually stimulating behaviours, teachers experienced higher job satisfaction, which in turn contributed to their effectiveness on the job.

Further supporting this perspective, Oruonyeije et al. (2024) examined schools in Enugu State and found a significant relationship between principals' individualized consideration and teachers' job performance. Their study suggested that when principals attended to the individual needs of their staff, it led to improved engagement and effectiveness among teachers. In addition, Umeh et al. (2024), reported that principals' efforts to intellectually stimulate teachers through encouraging innovation and critical thinking positively influenced teachers' professional output and classroom practices in Ebonyi State,. Unfortunately, there has been limited empirical validation of these claims within the context of public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone of Anambra State. It is against this background that this study investigated the relationship between principals' transformational leadership practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone.

Statement of the Problem

There is a concern that many school principals do not adequately exhibit transformational leadership behaviours such as motivating staff, encouraging professional development, or articulating a shared vision for school progress in the Otuocha Education Zone. This absence of effective leadership may result in diminished teacher morale, low motivation, weak commitment, and consequently, reduced instructional effectiveness.

Furthermore, the geographical and infrastructural realities of the zone present additional challenges. A significant number of secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone are situated in remote and hard-to-reach rural communities, often characterized by a lack of basic infrastructure and social amenities such as good roads, electricity, clean water, and healthcare services. These unfavourable conditions make such schools unattractive to many teachers, who are often reluctant to accept postings to these locations. The combination of difficult working environments and weak leadership practices may further demoralise teachers and compromise their effectiveness. If these issues remain unaddressed, they may continue to undermine the achievement of educational objectives within the zone. It is against this backdrop that the present study aims to examine the extent to which principals' transformational leadership practices correlate with teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools within Otuocha Education Zone of Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate the relationship between principals' transformational leadership practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone of Anambra State. Specifically, the study investigated the relationship between principals':

1. intellectual stimulation practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone of Anambra State.
2. individualized consideration practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone of Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between principals' intellectual stimulation practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone?
2. What is the relationship between principals' individualized consideration practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.0 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between principals' intellectual stimulation practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone.
2. There is no significant relationship between principals' individualized consideration practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone.

Research Method

The correlation survey research design was adopted for the study. The study was conducted in Otucha Education Zone of Anambra State. There are 29 public secondary schools in the zone. The population of the study comprised 686 teachers in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone. The sample of the study comprised 137 public secondary school teachers in the Zone. Using simple random sampling, the researcher sampled 20 percent of teachers in the zone. Two structured questionnaires were used to collect data for the study. The first questionnaire is titled "Principals Transformational leadership Practices Questionnaire (PTLQ)." The instrument has two clusters, 1 and 2. Cluster 1 contains 10 items on principals' intellectual stimulation practices. Cluster 2 contains 2 items on principals' individualized consideration practices. The second instrument is titled "Teachers Job Effectiveness Questionnaire (TJEQ)." The instrument contains 15 items on teachers job effectiveness. Both instruments were structured on a 4-point scale of Highly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Highly Disagree (SD). The face validation of the instruments was conducted by three experts in the Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus. The instruments reliability was ascertained through a trial test conducted on 20 teachers of public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone. The data collected was tested for internal consistency using Cronbach Alpha. This yielded reliability coefficients of 0.87 and 0.91 for clusters 1 and 2 respectively with a general reliability coefficient of 0.89 for PTLQ and 0.88 for TJEQ. Out of 137 copies of questionnaires administered, 128 copies were returned in good condition. Pearson product moment correlation was used to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses for the study.

In answering the research questions, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) was used to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between the variables. The interpretation of the r value is based on its magnitude. A correlation coefficient ranging from 0.00 to 0.19 is considered to indicate a very weak or negligible relationship. A value between 0.20 and 0.39 suggests a weak relationship, while a value between 0.40 and 0.59 reflects a moderate relationship. A correlation between 0.60 and 0.79 is regarded as high, and a value between 0.80 and 1.00 indicates a very high relationship. Positive values signify a direct relationship, meaning as one variable increases, the other tends to increase as well. Conversely, negative values indicate an inverse relationship, where an increase in one variable is associated with a decrease in the other.

In testing the hypotheses, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was applied to determine whether a statistically significant relationship exists between the variables. The decision to retain or reject each null

hypothesis was based on the p -value obtained from the analysis. If the p -value is less than or equal to 0.05 ($p \leq 0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there is a statistically significant relationship between the variables under consideration. However, if the p -value is greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$), the null hypothesis is not rejected, suggesting that there is no statistically significant relationship between the variables.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between principals' intellectual stimulation practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone?

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Correlation on the Relationship between Principals' Intellectual Stimulation Practices and Teachers' Job Effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools in Otuocha Education Zone

Variables			N	r	Remarks
Principals' Intellectual Stimulation Practices	Teachers' Job Effectiveness		128	0.70	High positive relationship

The result of the Pearson's correlation (r) presented in Table 1 shows that the correlation between principals' intellectual stimulation practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone was 0.70. This value indicates a high positive relationship. This implies that as principals' intellectual stimulation practices increases, teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools also increases and at a high rate. This indicates that there is a high positive relationship between principals' intellectual stimulation practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone.

Research Question 2

What is the relationship between principals' individualized consideration practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone?

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Correlation on the Relationship between Principals' Individualized Consideration Practices and Teachers' Job Effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools in Otuocha Education Zone

Variables			N	r	Remarks
Principals' Individualized Consideration Practices	Teachers' Job Effectiveness		128	0.69	High positive relationship

The result of the Pearson's correlation (r) presented in Table 2 shows that the correlation between principals' individualized consideration practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone was 0.69. This value indicates a high positive relationship. This implies that as principals' individualized consideration practices increases, teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools also increases and at a high rate. This indicates that there is a high positive relationship between principals'

individualized consideration practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between principals' intellectual stimulation practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone.

Table 3: Test of Significance of Pearson's Correlation between Principals' Intellectual Stimulation Practices and Teachers' Job Effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools in Otuocha Education Zone.

Variables	N	r	p-value	Remark
Principals' Intellectual Stimulation Practices Teachers' Job Effectiveness	128	0.70	0.00	Significant

The results in Table 3 show that there was a significant positive relationship between principals' intellectual stimulation practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone, $r = 0.70$, $p < 0.05$. Since the p-value was less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected, meaning that there was a significant relationship between principals' intellectual stimulation practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between principals' individualized consideration practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone.

Table 4: Test of Significance of Pearson's Correlation between Principals' Individualized Consideration Practices and Teachers' Job Effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools in Otuocha Education Zone.

Variables	N	r	p-value	Remark
Principals' Individualized Consideration Practices Teachers' Job Effectiveness	128	0.69	0.00	Significant

The results in Table 3 show that there was a significant positive relationship between principals' individualized consideration practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone, $r = 0.69$, $p < 0.05$. Since the p-value was less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected, meaning that there was a significant relationship between principals' individualized consideration practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone.

Discussion of Finding

The finding of the study revealed that there is a high positive relationship between principals' intellectual stimulation practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone. Two factors may account for this outcome. First, when principals encourage critical thinking and creativity among teachers, it empowers them to adopt innovative strategies in their teaching, thereby improving classroom

instruction. Second, principals who intellectually stimulate their staff challenge them to reflect on their professional practices and seek better approaches to problem-solving, which ultimately enhances job performance. This finding is in agreement with Umeh et al. (2024), who observed that principals' efforts to foster innovation and independent thinking among teachers significantly contributed to higher levels of professional output and improved classroom effectiveness in Ebonyi State. Similarly, Mba and Okoko (2024), in a study conducted in Bayelsa State, discovered a high positive correlation between principals' intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration and teachers' productivity. Their findings, drawn from data involving both principals and teachers, highlighted the critical role of these leadership practices in driving teacher performance. Likewise, Akinnubi and Adeoye (2024) found in Oyo State that principals who demonstrated intellectually stimulating behaviours created environments that fostered job satisfaction among teachers, leading to greater effectiveness in their duties.

Furthermore, the study also found a significant relationship between principals' intellectual stimulation practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone. This finding reinforces the idea that transformational leaders who engage their staff intellectually contribute meaningfully to teacher development and school improvement. As noted by Umeh et al. (2024), intellectually stimulating principals are instrumental in helping teachers become more effective by motivating them to rethink traditional methods and embrace new, more effective approaches to teaching and learning.

The finding of the study revealed a high positive relationship between principals' individualized consideration practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone. This suggests that when principals attend to the individual needs, strengths, and professional aspirations of their teachers, it leads to greater job satisfaction and higher levels of performance. One possible reason for this result is that individualized consideration helps to build trust and respect between school leaders and their staff, creating a supportive working atmosphere where teachers feel valued and motivated. Another reason could be that such leadership behaviour fosters continuous professional development, as teachers are more willing to engage in learning opportunities and improve their instructional practices when they feel supported. This finding is consistent with the assertion of Igwenwanne and Obasi (2024), who maintained that individualized consideration significantly enhances teachers' job performance by fostering emotional support and developmental mentoring. Similarly, Oruonyeije et al. (2024), in their study of secondary schools in Enugu State, concluded that when principals personalize their leadership approach and demonstrate empathy toward teachers' challenges and needs, it increases teacher morale and effectiveness. Supporting this view, Efendi (2015) noted that transformational leaders who give personal attention and guidance to staff members tend to improve the teachers' performance, motivation, and commitment to institutional goals. In addition, Umeh et al. (2024) found in a study conducted in Ebonyi State that individualized consideration by school leaders led to higher levels of engagement and job commitment among teachers, ultimately translating into improved teaching quality and student outcomes. Furthermore, the study also found a significant relationship between principals' individualized consideration practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone. This corroborates the findings of Asiegbu and Ikwu (2020), who observed that transformational leadership behaviours such as mentoring, support, and empathy are vital predictors of teachers' effectiveness and job satisfaction.

Conclusion

The findings of the study revealed that there is a significantly high positive relationship between principals' transformational leadership practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone. Findings revealed that principals' intellectual stimulation practices and individualized consideration practices have a high positive relationship with teachers job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Otuocha Education Zone. This implies that transformational leadership practices are essential tools for enhancing teacher job effectiveness in Otuocha Education Zone.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. The Ministry of Education and Post Primary Schools Services Commission (PPSSC) should organize regular training workshops and seminars to equip principals with skills in transformational leadership, especially in areas of intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration.
2. Principals should adopt supervisory approaches that prioritize mentoring, personalized feedback, and professional support rather than punitive or authoritarian methods.
3. The Anambra State Ministry of Education in collaboration with the PPSSC should revise leadership guidelines to emphasize transformational leadership traits in the recruitment, appointment and evaluation of secondary school principals.

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